

Point in Solid Test for Free-Form Solids Defined with Triangular Bézier Patches

Á.L. García, J. Ruiz de Miras, F.R. Feito

Departamento de Informática. Universidad de Jaén.
Paraje Las Lagunillas s/n. 23071 Jaén
SPAIN
e-mail: {algarcia, demiras, ffeito}@ujaen.es

Received: date / Revised version: date

Abstract A new algorithm to study the fundamental point in solid test for free-form solids is presented. The test is performed efficiently and robustly because it does not use trigonometric functions and it is not necessary to deal with complex special cases. The algorithm is based on considering the solid as composed of *original tetrahedra* and *free form cells*, and it computes the test in two stages: evaluation of the point inclusion in these simple elements, and merging of the results in a simple sum. The solid boundary is defined as a set of low-degree triangular Bézier patches.

Key words free-form solid modeling – extended simplicial chains – triangular Bézier patches – point in solid test – computer graphics algorithms

1 Introduction

The point in solid test may be stated as: given a point and a free-form solid, determine if the point is inside, outside or on the boundary of the solid. This test is the starting point for many other algorithms used in solid modelling (validity tests, edge classification, boolean operations, ...). Classic algorithms for testing the point inclusion are based on Jordan's theorem [3], which states that a half-line starting from the point has an odd number of intersections with the surface of the solid if the point is inside the solid, and an even number of intersections otherwise. The algorithms based on Jordan's theorem have to solve complex equation systems [24, 14, 8] (depending on the complexity of the free-form elements that define the solid surface), may be operationally unstable [12, 10], and have to deal with many

special cases [24, 9], for example, when the half-line is tangent with the surface of the solid.

We propose an algorithm to test the point in solid inclusion for free-form solids based on defining them by means of extended simplicial chains (ESC's) [18, 17, 15, 7]. This allows us to reduce the point in solid test to the merging of the results of the inclusion tests for the elements composing the ESC of the solid by means of a single sum.

In [6] simplicial chains (SC's) are presented as a mathematical formulation for geometric modelling in spaces of any dimension, particularising the concept of polyhedral chain defined by [23]. The use of simplicial chains is restricted to polyhedral solids, but by applying algebraic operations on them, it is possible to obtain any general polyhedral solid (manifold or non-manifold).

Simplicial chains are extended in [18, 15] by adding the concept of free-form cell (ffc), in order to be able to model manifold or non-manifold free-form solids. These have been called extended simplicial chains (ESC's), and are made of two different elements: simplices and ffc's. Firstly, algebraic patches were used to define the ffc's, although the ffc concept is independent of the surface patch used. In fact, in [7], the model has been extended to triangular Bézier patches.

In this paper we continue the work with triangular Bézier patches, developing a point in solid test for free-form solids described with ESC's defined using these patches. First, we will look at the basics of triangular Bézier patches (TBP's) and extended simplicial chains. Secondly, we will define the ffc using TBP's, and how we can test the point inclusion for this. Once having described the new kind of ffc, we will go on to describe the point in solid test and show the results we have obtained.

2 Triangular Bézier Patches (TBP's)

Triangular Bézier Patches (TBP's) [4, 2, 5, 22] were the first extension of the Bézier curves to surfaces, as a more

Send offprint requests to: Á.L. García

Correspondence to: Á.L. García (algarcia@ujaen.es)

Fig. 1 Control point net and parametric domain

Fig. 2 3-degree triangular Bézier patch

natural generalization than are tensor product patches. As with polygons, it is easier to model a surface with triangular elements than with square ones. Even the well-known GPU manufacturer ATI has developed the TRUFORM technology family that uses this kind of patches as a simple and efficient way to display smoother and more natural images [1, 22].

TBP's are defined by a triangular control point net with $\frac{1}{2} \cdot (n + 1) \cdot (n + 2)$ points (n being the degree of the patch). Each control point is named b_{ijk} , with $i \geq 0$, $j \geq 0$, $k \geq 0$, and $i + j + k = n$.

The parametric domain is triangular, having three parameters, u , v and w , that take value from the continuous interval $[0, 1]$; the sum $u+v+w$ always equals 1.0. In Fig. 1 we can see the control net from a 3-degree patch, and its parametric domain.

The surface is calculated using the Bernstein polynomials; for this kind of patch, these polynomials are given by:

$$B_{i,j,k}^n(u, v, w) = \binom{n}{i, j, k} \cdot u^i \cdot v^j \cdot w^k = \frac{n!}{i! \cdot j! \cdot k!} \cdot u^i \cdot v^j \cdot w^k;$$

Calling λ the 3-tuple (i, j, k) and τ the 3-tuple (u, v, w) , we obtain the expression for a n -degree TBP as:

$$b^n(\tau) = \sum_{|\lambda|=n} b_\lambda \cdot B_\lambda^n(\tau);$$

$|\lambda| = n$ stands for all the 3-tuples (i, j, k) which verify that $i + j + k = n$. Fig. 2 shows a 3-degree TBP with its associated control point net.

Every TBP is included in the convex hull of its control points, and interpolates b_{n00} , b_{0n0} and b_{00n} . The edges of the patch are Bézier curves whose control points are those on the edges of the control point mesh. These

properties will be useful when using TBP's in the next sections.

There are several interesting papers about TBP's, mainly describing how to use them to obtain a better free-form surface representation from an initial triangulation:

- Piper [13] uses an interpolation method similar to the Clough-Tocher one to obtain a C^0 continuous but visually smooth surface.
- Shirman and Séquin [21] construct a G^1 continuous surface by generating a mesh of 3-degree curves among the vertices, and filling the holes in that mesh with 4-degree TBP's together with square bicubic patches; it is said in their paper that their algorithm has limitations with very irregular surfaces.
- Kolb, Pottmann and Seidel [11] use the previous work of Shirman and Séquin [21] as a starting point to develop an algorithm with two variants. The first one uses 4-degree triangular patches, and the second one uses 7-degree triangular patches.
- The most recent paper being reviewed here is the one from Vlachos, Peters, Boyd and Mitchell [22]. They try to obtain a very simple and efficient algorithm, able to process each triangle independently. They use a quadratic interpolation to obtain the normal vector at each point of the patch, and calculate the control point mesh for 3-degree TBP's from the vertices and vertex normals of the initial triangulation.

In this paper, we will use the last mentioned method to obtain the patches we need for our purposes because of its simplicity and good adaptability to the fields of application of ESC's (efficient algorithms on free-form solids). Nevertheless, the proposed algorithm is general enough to be applied to any representation using TBP's of any degree.

3 Extended Simplicial Chains (ESC's)

ESC's [18, 15] are defined from SC's [6]. By means of the free-form cell (ffc) concept, ESC's allow us to treat free-form solids in a similar way that SC's do with polyhedral solids. Although the concept of ESC may be applied to any dimension, here our discussion is going to be restricted to 3D solids.

A 3-dimensional ESC is defined as:

$$\delta = \sum_i \alpha_i \cdot E_i;$$

The ESC δ is obtained as the sum of the extended cells E_i , each of them multiplied by an integer α_i (its coefficient). A 3D extended cell may be either a 3-dimensional simplex (a tetrahedron), or a free-form cell (ffc).

Each tetrahedron is defined from a triangle of the initial triangulation and an arbitrary origin point (the

same point for every tetrahedra of the same solid). These tetrahedra are called original tetrahedra, and the faces and edges that do not belong to the original triangulation of the solid are called original faces or original edges respectively. As it will be seen in section six, there is no problem if the origin point is coplanar with one or several triangles from the initial mesh.

Definition 1 (General free-form cell) *A general free-form cell [18, 15] is defined as a set of points in \mathbb{R}^3 obtained as the intersection of the half-spaces defined by a 3D free-form element and by one or more planar elements of dimension 2. This set of points verifies the following conditions:*

- It is a closed and connected set in \mathbb{R}^3 .
- Every point lies on the same connected component (sign-invariant) with regard to the implicit equation of the free-form element, except the ones of the boundary.
- The points common to a number of bound elements greater than or equal to 3 (the dimension of the ffc) also belong to the free-form element.

Each ffc has an associated sign (+1 or -1) depending on the orientation of the ffc with respect to the solid. If the associated sign is +1, then the ffc is added to the solid; if the sign is -1, then the ffc is subtracted from it. The coefficient of each ffc is equal to its sign. Later on we will explain a method to calculate this sign for a ffc defined by a TBP. As SC's do, each extended simplicial chain has an associated integer valued function, defined as:

$$f_\delta : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$$

$$f_\delta(\mathbf{Q}) = \sum_{\mathbf{Q} \in E_i} \alpha_i;$$

For each point \mathbf{Q} of the 3-dimensional space, this function takes as its value the result of the sum of the coefficients associated with the extended cells that contain \mathbf{Q} .

The free-form solid associated with an ESC is defined as the set of points that verify:

$$FF_\delta = \{\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^3 / f_\delta(\mathbf{Q}) \neq 0\};$$

The regularized operations with ESC's are similar to those with SC's, and have the same properties. Therefore, the set of ESC's with the regularized operations of sum of ESC's and product of an ESC by an integer has a vectorial space structure [18, 6].

Different ESC's can define the same free-form solid. In order to obtain a representative ESC for that solid, a *normal extended simplicial chain* is defined as the one that verifies:

$$f_\delta(\mathbf{Q}) = 1, \quad \forall \mathbf{Q} \in FF_\delta$$

Therefore, using ffc's we can treat the curved regions of a solid the same way we do using simplices for the

Fig. 3 Ffc defined by a TBP and planar elements

planar ones. Moreover, the ESC's inherit and extend the simplicity and homogeneity of the SC's for their use in free-form solid modelling. The algorithm to obtain the 3-dimensional ESC (defined by extended cells and its associated coefficients) from a free-form solid represented by an initial triangulation is given in [18, 7].

In [18, 17, 15], 3-dimensional ffc's are defined using algebraic patches as free-form elements, but it is emphasized that the concept of free-form cell is independent on both dimension and free-form element. In the following section and in [7], triangular Bézier patches (TBP's) are used to define 3-dimensional free-form cells.

4 Free-form Cell Defined by TBP's

In [15], once the ESC's have been defined using algebraic patches, it is said that this representation scheme does not depend on the kind of patch used to describe the surface of the solids. To use a different kind of patch, it is necessary to define the ffc using that kind of patch as free-form element, and a point inclusion test for that ffc. Once we have these, the theoretical basics and the algorithms with ESC's remain the same.

The intersection of the half-spaces defined by a 3D free-form element and one or more planes forms a ffc. If we use a TBP as free-form element, we could expect a 3-dimensional ffc to look like Fig. 3 (the planes are drawn using four edge polygons; the base triangle belongs to the initial triangulation of a solid).

The ffc would be limited by the TBP, the base triangle, and three planes. The TBP is obtained from the base triangle, using the algorithm from [22], so we need to know the vertex normals in order to obtain the control point net of the patch.

The three planes limiting the edges of the cell must be defined somehow to ensure that the ffc verifies the conditions described in the previous section. A first approach would be to use the planes which contain the points from the edges of the control point mesh, but we find the following problem:

When we described the TBP's, we said that the edges of every patch are Bézier curves defined by the control points of the edges of the control point mesh of the patch. As we can see in Fig. 4, it is possible to find TBP's whose control points from one or more edges of the control

Fig. 4 Top view of a TBP

point net do not lie on the same plane. Therefore, the Bézier curves defined by these points may not lie on a plane. In Fig. 4, the plane that contains three control points of an edge is drawn with a black line, and the remaining point lies outside that plane.

As the boundaries of the TBP's are curves that are often not contained in planes and the lateral boundaries of the ffc are planar, it seems obvious that it will be necessary to use the neighbour patches to obtain a completely closed set as stated in definition 1.

Another possible approach for defining the planar boundaries of the ffc could be to use planes parallel to the base triangle normal vector, but in this case there would be holes between neighbour cells that will lead to a more complicated algorithm. One more idea was to use the planes that contain the original faces of the tetrahedra, but in this case an unfortunate election of the origin point would cause a high percentage of use of the neighbour patches to compute the inclusion algorithm, as it can be seen in Fig. 5; this issue will be clearer after definition 3.

So, it is necessary to define more precisely the ffc defined by a TBP. First of all, we will define the planes that will be used, and afterwards we will give the definition of the ffc.

Definition 2 (Plane associated to two triangles)

Let t_1 and t_2 be two triangles from the initial triangulation of a free-form solid that share a common edge e . The plane associated to t_1 and t_2 , noted $\pi(t_1, t_2)$, is the plane that contains the edge e and is parallel to the weighted average of the normal vectors from t_1 and t_2 .

Using these planes, we define a free-form cell as follows:

Definition 3 (Free-form cell defined with TBP's)

Let S be a free-form solid whose surface is represented by a set of TBP's, let $b(\tau)$ be a patch of this set, and let t_0 be its base triangle (t_1 , t_2 and t_3 being its edge-

Fig. 5 Schematic view of the influence of the election of the associated planes in the construction of the free-form cells

neighbourhood). A free-form cell of S is defined as the intersection of the half-spaces determined by:

- The three associated planes $\pi(t_0, t_1)$, $\pi(t_0, t_2)$ and $\pi(t_0, t_3)$,
- The base triangle t_0 ,
- $b(\tau)$, and
- All the TBP's that share at least one vertex with $b(\tau)$ and are totally or partially included in the intersection of the half-spaces determined by the planar elements.

There are several well known possible choices for the weights used to compute the average of the normal vectors from t_1 and t_2 to obtain the associated planes, like the areas of the triangles or any angle-related value. For our purposes, it is desirable that only a minimum number of neighbouring patches are included in the intersection of the half-spaces determined by the associated planes, because the resulting ffc will then be simpler. In Fig. 5, a schematic view of this problem can be seen; supposing the white dots as the union of neighbouring patches, the choice of planes represented by the dashed lines would result in a ffc bounded by a higher number of patches than the ffc resulting from the other choice.

Fig. 6 shows an example of a free-form cell. The neighbouring TBP's are drawn in wireframe mode to allow a better understanding of the image.

If the TBP passes through the base triangle, then each connected component is considered as a different ffc, as shown in Fig. 7 (the base triangle is drawn in red, and each ffc is filled with a different colour).

Even though the TBP passes through the base triangle, it is not necessary for our algorithm to compute the intersection curve between the patch and the triangle, because we only consider the position of the point to be tested with respect to the bounding elements of the ffc.

We have defined a ffc using not only the corresponding triangle from an initial triangulation of a solid, but also the neighbouring ones. This implies that it is necessary to use a complete and correct triangulation of the solid in order to obtain the correct ffc's. Complete and

Fig. 6 Ffc as described in this paper

Fig. 7 View of two ffc's that share the same patch

Fig. 8 Ray traced from the point in the direction of the base triangle normal

correct triangulation stands for a closed triangle mesh in which each edge is shared by two triangles.

5 Point Inclusion in a Ffc

ESC's make the implementation of the main solid modelling algorithms much easier by means of operating on the extended cells, f.e. octree conversion, polygonalization and voxelization of solids [19, 20]. This dramatically reduces the number of special cases, and therefore makes these algorithms more robust and efficient.

To develop the point in solid test algorithm, we need to find a way to determine if a point is inside or outside a ffc as described in the previous section. We propose an algorithm based on intersecting the elements which limit the ffc with a ray traced from the point following the direction given by the base triangle normal; see Fig. 8.

The ray will intersect each planar bounding element of the ffc one or zero times (if the sign of an intersection point with regard to the plane that contains the base

Fig. 9 Planes we use in our first test

Fig. 10 Schematic view in 2D of a TBP and five points

triangle of the ffc is distinct from the sign of the ffc, that point is ignored); due to the low degree of the patches, there will be at most one intersection with each TBP in a high percentage of cases (more than 99% in our experiments, see section 7); in this situation, if the point to be classified is located between the base triangle and the nearest intersection point to the base triangle, then the point is inside the ffc. In those special situations where there are more than one intersection point with any TBP, the intersection points must be sorted, and a more careful study of the relative position of the point to be classified is needed; this is also valid when using patches of a higher degree. These situations are easily detected in our algorithm.

Obtaining the intersection of a ray and a TBP is a very complex task. As we don't need to know the exact intersection point, we use triangle meshes with different levels of detail to approximate only the patches that are strictly needed to compute the inclusion algorithm for the given point. The algorithm is as follows:

- First of all, we test that the point is inside the intersection of the half-spaces defined by the associated planes and the planes parallel to the base triangle, which contain the control points placed furthest from that triangle (if every control point is at the same side of the base triangle, one of the planes will be the one containing this triangle). See Fig. 9. If the point is outside the intersection of these half-spaces, the point is outside the ffc, and it is not necessary to tessellate the corresponding patch.
- If the point is inside the half-spaces, then we intersect the ray with a triangulation of each patch. If there is only one intersection with one patch, we will do as follows (see Fig. 10):
 1. If the intersection point is at the same side with respect to the base triangle than the point, and it is further from the base triangle than the point,

Fig. 11 Choice of the starting point to count the number of intersections of the ray (schematic view). For Q_1 , the starting point is the intersection of the ray with the associated plane, and for Q_2 , it is the intersection with the base triangle

then that point is inside the ffc. This is the situation for points **A** and **B**.

2. If the intersection point is at the same side with respect to the base triangle than the point, and it is a vertex of the triangulation which is not further from the base triangle than the point, then that point is outside the ffc. See point **C**.
3. If the intersection point is a vertex of the triangulation, and it is equal to the point to be tested, then the point is on the surface of the ffc. See point **E**.
4. If the intersection point is at the same side of the base triangle, and it is not further from the base triangle than the point, we must increment the level of detail only in that triangle, because we cannot ensure that the point is outside the ffc. As is the case for point **D**.

If the level of detail of the triangulation of the main patch is small enough and we still cannot ensure the position of the point, then we will consider the point as placed outside the ffc.

- If exceptionally there are more than one intersection with the patches, the intersections are refined and sorted, and we have to check the number of intersections between the base triangle (or the intersection with the associated planes, see Fig 11) and the point to be classified. If there are zero or an even number of intersections, the point is inside the ffc, otherwise it is outside.

Fig. 12 shows the refinement process for a point and a TBP using level of detail=1. The level of detail is interpreted as the number of vertices evaluated over each edge of a previously computed triangle [22]. The vertices are therefore obtained by evaluation of the patch at uniformly distributed parameter values.

This algorithm deals uniformly with all the ffc's, without taking care of the form of the associated TBP's.

We are going to show an implementation of the algorithm in pseudo code. The return value is 0 if the point is outside the ffc, 1 if the point is inside the ffc, and 2 if the point is on the border of the ffc.

Fig. 12 Triangles calculated with our algorithm

```

function pointInclusionTest ( point Q )
{
  if Q is outside the half-spaces determined by the
  planar elements
    return 0; /* Out */

  construct a ray with Q and the normal vector of the
  base triangle

  intersect the ray with triangulations of the patches

  if there are only one intersection P with TBP's
  {
    if P and Q are at the same side w.r.t. the plane that
    contains the base triangle
    {
      if P is further from the base triangle than Q
        return 1; /* In */

      if P is a vertex of the triangulation of the patch
      {
        if P equals Q
          return 2; /* On the border */
        else
          return 0; /* Out */
      }
      else
        increment level of detail and repeat process
    }
    else
      return 0; /* Out */
  }
  else
  {
    if Q equals any intersection
      return 2; /* On the border */

    sort intersections

    choose the starting point

    count the number of intersections between the
    starting point and the point to be classified

    if the number of intersections is even
      return 1; /* In */
    else
      return 0; /* Out */
  }
}

```

}
}

6 Point in Solid Test for a Free-Form Solid

Once we have explained the way we represent free-form solids using ESC's, and how we can test the point inclusion for any ffc, we will go on explaining the point inclusion algorithm for a whole free-form solid.

The test we propose has very few special cases to deal with. This allow the algorithm to be simple and operationally stable. Suppose we represent the solids by normal ESC's, made of original tetrahedra and ffc's. The test is performed by means of testing the point inclusion for each extended cell (ffc's and tetrahedra) of the normal ESC representing the solid, and combining the results in a single sum, as explained in [17,15]. In those papers, a theorem is presented and proved to test the point inclusion using ESC's. We use the same algorithm, changing the kind of ffc's used.

The point inclusion in a tetrahedron can be tested by means of calculating the barycentric coordinates of the point with regards to the tetrahedron. This can be done as follows:

Definition 4 (Barycentric coordinates) *Let \mathbf{Q} be a 3-D point and \mathbf{T} a tetrahedron of vertices $\{\mathbf{T}_1, \mathbf{T}_2, \mathbf{T}_3, \mathbf{T}_4\}$. The tuple $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4)$ is said to be the barycentric coordinates of \mathbf{Q} with regards to the tetrahedron \mathbf{T} iff verifies:*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q} &= \alpha_1 \cdot \mathbf{T}_1 + \alpha_2 \cdot \mathbf{T}_2 + \alpha_3 \cdot \mathbf{T}_3 + \alpha_4 \cdot \mathbf{T}_4; \\ \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 &= 1; \end{aligned}$$

Using matrix notation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Q}.x \\ \mathbf{Q}.y \\ \mathbf{Q}.z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{T}_1.x & \mathbf{T}_2.x & \mathbf{T}_3.x & \mathbf{T}_4.x \\ \mathbf{T}_1.y & \mathbf{T}_2.y & \mathbf{T}_3.y & \mathbf{T}_4.y \\ \mathbf{T}_1.z & \mathbf{T}_2.z & \mathbf{T}_3.z & \mathbf{T}_4.z \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{pmatrix};$$

Therefore, we can obtain the barycentric coordinates for \mathbf{Q} this way:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{T}_1.x & \mathbf{T}_2.x & \mathbf{T}_3.x & \mathbf{T}_4.x \\ \mathbf{T}_1.y & \mathbf{T}_2.y & \mathbf{T}_3.y & \mathbf{T}_4.y \\ \mathbf{T}_1.z & \mathbf{T}_2.z & \mathbf{T}_3.z & \mathbf{T}_4.z \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Q}.x \\ \mathbf{Q}.y \\ \mathbf{Q}.z \\ 1 \end{pmatrix};$$

- If $\alpha_i > 0 \forall i \in [1, 4]$, then \mathbf{Q} is inside \mathbf{T} .
- If at least one $\alpha_i < 0$ with $i \in [1, 4]$, then \mathbf{Q} is outside \mathbf{T} .
- If one of the coordinates $\alpha_j = 0$, and $\alpha_i > 0 \forall i \neq j$, then \mathbf{Q} is on the face of \mathbf{T} defined by the vertices \mathbf{T}_i ($i \neq j$).
- If two of the coordinates $\alpha_j = 0$, $\alpha_k = 0$, and $\alpha_i > 0 \forall i \neq j, i \neq k$, then \mathbf{Q} is on the edge defined by the vertices \mathbf{T}_i ($i \neq j, i \neq k$).

Fig. 13 The ffc filled with green is positive, and the one filled with blue is negative

- If three of the coordinates $\alpha_j = 0$, $\alpha_k = 0$, $\alpha_l = 0$, then $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{T}_i$ ($i \neq j, i \neq k, i \neq l$).

Once the inclusion value for each extended cell is obtained, we can merge the results in a single sum to obtain the presence value for that point. In [17,15] a theorem is stated about this sum. In brief, what we have to do is to sum the coefficient associated with the extended cells that contain the point, bearing in mind the situations in which a point is in the border between two cells. If the sum equals 1 (that value implies for us presence of the solid, as we are considering normal ESC's), then the point is inside the solid; otherwise the point is outside. Remember that the extended cells can overlap, and therefore a point may belong to several cells.

The coefficient associated with each tetrahedra is calculated as the sign (+1 or -1) of its signed volume, calculated as:

$$\frac{1}{6} \cdot \begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{T}_1.x & \mathbf{T}_2.x & \mathbf{T}_3.x & \mathbf{T}_4.x \\ \mathbf{T}_1.y & \mathbf{T}_2.y & \mathbf{T}_3.y & \mathbf{T}_4.y \\ \mathbf{T}_1.z & \mathbf{T}_2.z & \mathbf{T}_3.z & \mathbf{T}_4.z \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

If the signed volume of a tetrahedron is 0, the associated coefficient will also be 0. This is not a problem, because the ESC model deal with these cells in the same way than with any other cell.

The coefficient (+1 or -1) associated with each ffc for a given point depends on the position of the point with regard to the plane that contains the base triangle. This plane is determined by the vertices and the normal vector of the triangle (suppose the vertices of the triangle to be given in counterclockwise). See Fig. 13.

As stated above, we have to bear in mind the situations where a point is in the border between two or more extended cells. In these cases, the solution is obtained by means of distributing the coefficient among the extended cells which share the point. We can see these situations in Fig. 14. It shows twelve extended cells obtained from half of an initial triangulation which represents a cube:

- If the point is on an original face of a tetrahedron, it belongs to two different tetrahedra. In Fig. 14, point $\mathbf{Q1}$ belongs to both tetrahedra $\mathbf{T5}$ and $\mathbf{T6}$. Each original tetrahedron contributes with $+\frac{1}{2}$ or $-\frac{1}{2}$ depending on their sign.

Fig. 14 a) Initial triangulation. b) Points, original tetrahedra and free-form cells

- If the point is on an original edge of a tetrahedron, it may belong to many tetrahedra. In Fig. 14, point **Q2** belongs to the six tetrahedra represented. In this situation, we only sum $+1$ once for all original tetrahedra with positive sign, and -1 only once for all original tetrahedra with negative sign.
- If the point is on the base triangle of a ffc, it belongs to the ffc and the original tetrahedron whose basis is the same triangle. In Fig. 14, point **Q3** belongs to both tetrahedron **T6** and free-form cell ffc6. Each extended cell contributes with $+\frac{1}{2}$ or $-\frac{1}{2}$ depending on their sign.
- If the point is on an edge of a base triangle, it is shared by two ffc's and two original tetrahedra. In Fig. 14, point **Q4** is shared by tetrahedra **T1** and **T6**, and free-form cells ffc1 and ffc6. In this situation, we only sum once $+1$ or -1 when the sign of a tetrahedron and its corresponding ffc are the same.
- If the point is on one of the planes that limit a ffc, the point belongs to the two ffc's that are limited by that plane. In Fig. 14, see point **Q5**. In this case, each ffc contributes to the sum with $+\frac{1}{2}$ or $-\frac{1}{2}$ depending on their sign.

So, we have to know when the special cases appear. Using barycentric coordinates for tetrahedra allows us to control this for the simplices. For the ffc's, once we know that the point is inside the ffc, we have to test if it is on one of the associated planes, or in the base triangle; therefore, the return values for the point inclusion test comprises: inside, outside, on the base triangle, on one edge of the base triangle, on the TBP (therefore on the boundary of the solid), and on one lateral plane.

Next, we show a pseudo code of the inclusion test for the whole solid. The function returns 2 if the point is on the boundary of the solid, 1 if the point is inside it, and 0 if it is outside.

We use three sets of edges to control the situations where a point is in the border of two or more cells. The meaning of these sets is as follows:

- $V+$: set of original edges (between the origin of the tetrahedra and one vertex from the original triangulation) containing the point and belonging to original tetrahedra with positive orientation (sign).
- $V-$: set of original edges (between the origin of the tetrahedra and one vertex from the original triangulation)

lation) containing the point and belonging to original tetrahedra with negative orientation (sign).

- V_p : set of edges from the original triangulation containing the point.

Each edge is contained only once in its corresponding set.

About the code shown:

- The signs of the tetrahedra and ffc's are computed as explained earlier.
- The function *processInclusionFfc* returns the value to be accumulated in the resulting sum according to the inclusion value for a ffc. This function brings the set V_p up-to-date. The value returned is the sign of the ffc if the point is inside the ffc or on the TBP, or on a non processed edge of the base triangle; 0 if the point is outside the ffc, and half the sign of the ffc if the point is on a lateral plane or on the base triangle. See [15,17] for more details.
- The function *inclusionTetrahedron* calculates the barycentric coordinates of the point with regards to the tetrahedron, and returns a value depending on the position of the point: outside the tetrahedron (0), inside the tetrahedron (1), on a face of the tetrahedron (2), on an original edge of the tetrahedron (3), or on an edge of the base triangle (4).
- The function *processInclusionTet* returns the value to be accumulated in the resulting sum according to the inclusion value for a tetrahedron. This function brings the sets V_+ and V_- up-to-date. The value returned is the sign of the tetrahedron if the point is inside it, or on a non processed original edge of the tetrahedron; 0 if the point is outside the tetrahedron, or if it is on an edge of the base triangle; and half the sign of the tetrahedron if the point is on an original face of it. See [15,17] for more details.

```

function pointInclusionInSolid ( point Q )
{
  inclusion = 0.0;

  foreach freeFormCell ffc in the solid
  {
    construct original tetrahedron T with origin
      origin point O and the base triangle of ffc

    sT = sign of the original tetrahedron T;

    /* Test the inclusion in the ffc */
    resultFfc = ffc.pointInclusionTest ( Q );
    if resultFfc  $\neq$  0
    {
      if resultFfc equals 2
        return 2; /* On the boundary */

      sFfc = sign of the ffc;
      inclusion += processInclusionFfc
    }
  }

```

```

/* Test the inclusion in the original tetrahedron */
resultT = T.inclusionTetrahedron ( Q );
if resultT  $\neq$  0
  inclusion += processInclusionTet
}

if inclusion equals 1.0
  return 1; /* In */
else
  return 0; /* Out */
}

```

This algorithm avoids the use of a full high level triangulation of the solid nor an iterative one, because we will only have to use the polygonalization of the patches for a very low percentage of points. This is due to the fact that most of the points are not included in the intersection of the half-spaces defined by the planar elements of the ffc's, and therefore we will only have to deal with the inclusion in the original tetrahedra. Moreover, when it is necessary to work with the polygonalization of the patches, most of the times it will not be necessary to reach the highest level of detail.

The algorithm is robust because the number of special cases is very low, and they are easy to detect and handle. Numerically, this algorithm presents the same trouble as other, due to the limited precision of every computer system when performing floating point operations; this is a well-known problem for every algorithm that try to solve this and other solid modelling tasks, and that is the reason why we use a threshold value when applying relational operators to floating point values.

The ESC of a solid will have as many simplices as the number of triangles of the initial triangulation, and the number of ffc's will be at most twice the number of simplices. The test comprises a traversal through the extended cells, computing the local inclusion test for each cell as explained before and accumulating the results. The time complexity for the computation on each simplex is constant, and for each ffc it is quadratic with respect to the level of detail used to tessellate the patches; the total time complexity of the algorithm is therefore linear with respect to the number of triangles of the initial triangulation of the solid. A practical time study of time complexity is given in section 7.

7 Results

It is important to remark that the time taken by the inclusion algorithm for the ffc's depends on the starting level of detail, because the number of iterations the algorithm has to do is inversely proportional to the level of detail. However, as the level of detail increases, the number of vertices the algorithm has to evaluate to triangulate the TBP's grows up more quickly. It is therefore

Fig. 15 Stomach (533 TBP's). a) Initial triangulation b) Solid limited by TBP's

Fig. 16 Liver (273 TBP's). a) Initial triangulation b) Solid limited by TBP's

Fig. 17 Mushroom (448 TBP's). a) Initial triangulation b) Solid limited by TBP's

necessary to select the level of detail taking into account these two aspects.

Figs. 15, 16 and 17 show three meshes we have used for our tests. They show the flat shaded initial triangulation and the free-form solid limited by TBP's.

Tables 1 and 2 show the results that we have obtained with our algorithm. In our tests, we used different sets of points regularly distributed inside the bounding box of the control point nets of the TBP's (Fig. 18 shows the result of one of the tests). We compared the number of intersections that we had to calculate with the number of intersections to be calculated according to Jordan's theorem. To obtain this last value, we counted the number of intersections of a half-line starting from the point to be tested in the direction of the Y axis with the convex hull of the control point nets from the TBP's. For our algorithm we used the following parameter values: level of detail = 10; the precision limit in the parametric domain is 10^{-5} . The values marked in bold in these two tables are the best results for each point set.

Fig. 18 Result of the test for a model and a set of points

In Fig. 19 we can see graphically the evolution of the number of intersections to calculate versus the number of points used for both our algorithm and the ones based on Jordan's theorem.

As we can see from the results, the new algorithm does not need to compute as many intersections as the ones based on Jordan's theorem. This is due to the fact that in most of the situations the point to be studied is inside an original tetrahedron and out of any ffc as can be seen in Fig. 14; it is therefore not necessary to calculate any intersection for that point. Moreover, the test we propose is simpler and consequently it reduces the number of special cases with respect to others.

We have also studied the time efficiency of the algorithm on a desktop PC based on an Intel Pentium IV 2.4 GHz processor, with 512 MB of DDR RAM. Each row of Table 3 contains a breakdown of the time spent to load a model. The first column of the table shows the time necessary to read the initial triangulation from a file that stores vertex coordinates and triangles (as triads of vertex indices); the loading of the mesh includes also the computation of topological relations among triangles. The second column of the table shows the time necessary to construct the ESC that represents the solid, including the computation of the control point net of the patches, the simplices and the ffc's. Optionally, as an optimization, it can be interesting to precompute the tessellation of the TBP's, in order to increase the performance of the algorithm; the third and fourth column of the table show the time spent to compute the initial triangulation of the patches and two refinement steps, respectively (the starting level of detail is 8). As it can be seen, the computations are not time expensive.

Table 1 Results obtained with the stomach model (533 TBP's)

Number of points	Jordan		ESC's	
	Intersections	Intersections/point	Intersections	Intersections/point
1000 (10*10*10)	611	0.611	58	0.058
1728 (12*12*12)	1116	0.645833333	229	0.132523148
2744 (14*14*14)	1767	0.643950437	378	0.137755102
3375 (15*15*15)	2208	0.654222222	399	0.118222222
4096 (16*16*16)	2697	0.658447266	609	0.148681641
4913 (17*17*17)	3251	0.661713820	610	0.124160391

Table 2 Results obtained with the liver model (273 TBP's)

Number of points	Jordan		ESC's	
	Intersections	Intersections/point	Intersections	Intersections/point
1000 (10*10*10)	816	0.816	147	0.147
1728 (12*12*12)	1466	0.848379630	303	0.175347222
2744 (14*14*14)	2349	0.856049563	566	0.206268222
3375 (15*15*15)	2872	0.850962963	681	0.201777778
4096 (16*16*16)	3558	0.868652344	741	0.180908203
4913 (17*17*17)	4321	0.879503358	940	0.191329127

Fig. 19 Plot of the results from the tests**Table 3** Breakdown of the time spent to load some models (in seconds)

Mesh	Loading time	ESC construction time	Tessellation time 1	Tessellation time 2
Stomach	0.300	0.076	0.360	29.336
Liver	0.083	0.040	0.180	14.696
Mushroom	0.213	0.063	0.300	24.420

Table 4 Summary of the usage of TBP's to construct the free-form cells

Mesh	TBP's	ffc's	Avg.
Stomach	534	818	2.587
Liver	274	422	2.600
Mushroom	448	694	2.687

Fig. 20 Result of our tests with the stomach mesh and a $100*100*100$ regular set of points

Table 4 shows information about the construction of the ffc's. It contains the number of TBP's that bound the solids, the total number of ffc's resulting from the construction of the ESC's, and the average number of TBP's that are required to construct each cell. Most of the ffc's require one or several neighbouring patches to completely close their volume, and therefore one TBP can take part in the definition of several ffc's.

A time reference for the inclusion test can be seen at Table 5, together with figures of the results (Figs. 20, 21, 22). They show the time and visual results for a $100*100*100$ regular set of points, using 8 as level of detail and two refinement steps for our algorithm. The figures are obtained by blending pictures of the results with pictures of the solids bounded by TBP's.

The first column in Table 5 shows the total time; the second one shows the average time spent to test the inclusion of a point; the third one shows the total number of rays used to compute the inclusion tests, and the fourth one shows the average number of rays per point.

Finally, as previously mentioned in section 5, Table 6 shows the number of rays which intersect more than once the same patch when testing the inclusion in a ffc, and its percentage with respect to the total number of rays. Thanks to the kind of patches used and its low degree, these situations are very rare.

Fig. 22 Result of our tests with the mushroom mesh and a $100*100*100$ regular set of points**Table 6** Rays which intersect more than once the same patch when testing inclusion

Mesh	Rays	Total number of rays	%
Stomach	162	64050	0.25%
Liver	156	142886	0.11%
Mushroom	0	64156	0.00%

8 Conclusions

A new robust and simple algorithm to study the inclusion test of points for free-form solids has been presented. It does not need to solve complex equation systems, and the number of special cases is minimum; moreover, these special cases are detected and treated simply and homogeneously. Because of the way it works, it may be very suitable for its parallelization or even hardware implementation. Although it needs to compute ray intersec-

Table 5 Time results when testing the inclusion of a 100*100*100 regular set of points

Mesh	Time	Avg. per point	Rays	Avg. per point
Stomach	19 m. 31 s.	0.001171 s.	64050	0.064050
Liver	8 m. 32 s.	0.000512 s.	142886	0.142886
Mushroom	15 m. 19 s.	0.000919 s.	64156	0.064156

tions, the number of them is very low when compared with the classic algorithms based on Jordan's theorem.

Given that this test is the basis for many other solid modelling algorithms, its relevance is maximum. Although considering the free-form solids as composed of ffc's and original tetrahedra could suppose a high number of calculations, as we have shown, both constructing and operating with these extended cells is really simple; moreover, it is not necessary to maintain expensive or very special data structures to operate with ESC's. Since the cells may have common zones, many operations may be simplified and optimized [16, 19].

Acknowledgements This work has been partially granted by the Ministry of Science and Technology of Spain and the European Union by means of the ERDF funds, under the research project TIC2001-2099-C03-03

References

- ATI Technologies, Inc. Truform white paper, 2001.
- W. Böhm, G. Farin, and J. Kahmann. A survey of curve and surface methods in CAGD. *Computer Aided Geometric Design*, 1:1–60, 1984.
- P. do Carmo. *Differential Geometry of Curves and Surfaces*. Prentice-Hall, NJ, 1976.
- G. Farin. Triangular Bernstein-Bézier patches. *Computer Aided Geometric Design*, 3:83–127, 1986.
- G. Farin. *Curves and Surfaces for Computer Aided Geometric Design. A Practical Guide*. Academic Press, San Diego, 1993.
- F. Feito and M. Rivero. Geometric modelling based on simplicial chains. *Computers & Graphics*, 22(5):611–619, 1998.
- Á. García, J. Ruiz, and F. Feito. Free-form solid modelling based on extended simplicial chains using triangular bézier patches. *Computers & Graphics*, 27(1):27–39, February 2003.
- C. Hu, N. Patrikalakis, and X. Ye. Robust interval solid modelling. Part I: Representations. *Computer Aided Design*, 28(10):807–817, 1996.
- K. Hui. A robust point inclusion algorithm for regions bounded by parametric curve segments. *Computer Aided Design*, 29(11):771–778, 1997.
- J. Keyser, S. Krishnan, and D. Manocha. Efficient and accurate B-rep generation of low degree sculptured solids using exact arithmetic. In C. Hoffmann and W. Bronsvort, editors, *Fourth Symposium on Solid Modeling and Applications*, pages 42–55, Atlanta, GA, May 1997. Solid Modeling Association, ACM Press.
- A. Kolb, H. Pottmann, and H. Seidel. Fast and fair surface reconstruction. Technical Report TR-1995-2, Universität Erlangen, 1995.
- S. Krishnan and D. Manocha. Efficient representations and techniques for computing B-reps of CSG models with NURBS primitives. In *CSG '96*, pages 101–122, Winchester, U.K., 1996. Informations Geometers Ltd.
- B. Piper. *Geometric Modeling: Algorithms and New Trends*, chapter Visually Smooth Interpolation with Triangular Bézier Patches, pages 221–233. SIAM, Philadelphia, 1987.
- F. Preparata and M. Shamos. *Computational Geometry: An Introduction*. Springer Verlag, New York, 1985.
- J. Ruiz. *Free-Form Solid Modeling*. PhD thesis, Universidad de Granada, Granada, Spain, 2001.
- J. Ruiz and F. Feito. B-rep-octree conversion for free-form solids. In *VIII Spanish Conference on Computer Graphics*, Ourense, Spain, 1998. in spanish.
- J. Ruiz and F. Feito. Inclusion test for free-form solids. *Computers & Graphics*, 23:255–268, 1999.
- J. Ruiz and F. Feito. Mathematical free-form solid modeling based on extended simplicial chains. In *WSCG '99: VII Conference on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Interactive Digital Media*, pages 241–248, Plzen-Bory, Czech Republic, 1999.
- J. Ruiz and F. Feito. ESC-MOD: Experimental system for free-form solid modeling. In *XI Spanish Conference on Computer Graphics*, Girona, Spain, 2001. in spanish.
- J. Ruiz and F. Feito. Direct and robust voxelization and polygonalization of free-form csg solids. In *3DVPT 2002: 1st International Symposium on 3D Data Processing, Visualization and Transmission*, Padova, Italy, 2002.
- L. Shirman and C. Séquin. Local surface interpolation with Bézier patches. *Computer Aided Geometric Design*, 4:279–295, 1987.
- A. Vlachos, J. Peters, C. Boyd, and J. Mitchell. Curved PN triangles. In *ACM Symposium on Interactive 3D Graphics*, pages 159–166, New York, 2001. ACM, ACM Press.
- H. Whitney. *Geometric Integration Theory*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 1957.
- J. Ying and N. Sugie. A point-inclusion algorithm for a domain with boundary composed of algebraic curve segments. *Systems and Computers in Japan*, 22:1823–1829, 1991.